

The Impact of High Work Performance Practices on Hospital Employee Performance: The Mediation Moderation of Employee Engagement and Employee Extra Role

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ARTICLE INFO	ABSTRACT
Published Online: 04 July 2022	<p>Purpose – This study aimed to determine the determinants of employee performance at Zainoel Abidin General Hospital, and how it affects the employee performance at this hospital. In addition, to find out whether the extra role can serve as a moderating variable on the influence of high-performance work practices on employee performance.</p> <p>Design/methodology/approach – The sampling technique used in this study is simple probability sampling. The sample count is 217, calculated using the Slovin formula with an error rate of 5%. Primary data collection is carried out using a 5-point questionnaire on the Likert scale and depth interview with several key informants information from the in-depth interview can also be used to support finding from quantitative analysis. It is processed using AMOS 26.0.</p> <p>Findings – There is a significant effect of high-performance work practices (HWP) on employee engagement and employee performance. The effect of employee engagement on employee performance is also significant. When compared between these two determinant variables and their effect on employee performance, the high-performance work practice (HWP) has a larger magnitude so that the impact on improving employee performance will be greater than employee involvement. The results of testing moderating hypotheses also show significant results. The employee's extra role can increase the magnitude of the influence of high-performance work practices on employee performance and employee involvement in employee performance.</p> <p>Limitations/research implications – Future research can develop a wider sample of hospital customers that is not only limited scope in one city but several cities within the Aceh province so that the findings will be more comprehensive.</p> <p>Originality/value – During this time, most strategic HWP research focused more on the manufacturing sector that cannot be generalized to the service sector because of its different characteristics. In this study, the author applied the concept of HWP to the service sector (health services in hospitals).</p>
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KEYWORDS: High Work Performance Practices, Employee Performance, Employee Engagement, and Employee Extra Role	

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background

Regional General Hospital (RSUD) dr. Zainoel Abidin Banda Aceh operates as a working unit of the Aceh Government to provide public services whose management is based on the delegation of authority by the Aceh Government. In other words, RSUD dr. Zainoel Abidin Banda Aceh is part of the regional apparatus in achieving the goals of the Aceh Government which is inseparable from the Aceh Government as the parent. This Aceh Working Unit manages the provision

of health services and health education in line with sound business practices. In the structure of the Aceh Government, the Regional General Hospital dr. Zainoel Abidin Banda Aceh is a regional technical institution that provides health services to the community and serves as a referral center for the province of Aceh and education. Regional General Hospital dr.

Hospital services have their characteristics. This characteristic is caused by the hospital being a very complex organization. The complexity and characteristics of hospital services need to be known and understood by everyone who has

“The Impact of High Work Performance Practices on Hospital Employee Performance: The Mediation Moderation of Employee Engagement and Employee Extra Role”

duties and responsibilities in the development and operation of hospitals.

The complexity of the hospital is partly due to the existence of various activities that are sometimes contradictory and often even lead to conflict. The conflict is mainly caused by the presence of various personnel with different educational backgrounds ranging from highly educated and skilled personnel to uneducated staff. Talented conflicts occur between the medical profession and the management profession caused on the one hand using a medical clinical approach while on the other hand using a managerial approach. As a health service provider institution, the role of employee knowledge and expertise is very important in improving the performance of the hospital. The knowledge and expertise of employees help develop the company's intangible assets.

The performance of employees at Zainoel Abidin Hospital Banda Aceh has not been as expected. From the 2020 LAKIP data, it can be seen that the performance achievements of the Zainoel Abidin hospital on the main performance indicators as informed through the 2020 LAKIP report, did not all meet expectations. In the Bed Occupancy Rate (BOR) indicator, the target is 74% but the realization is only 48.46%. Likewise, the Turn Over Interval (TOI) indicator, namely the length of time the bed is not occupied from one patient to another, which was targeted at 1.45 days, turned out to be 4.45 days. This indicates that the patient's bed has been empty for too long (not filled). The Average Length of Stay (ALoS) indicator has also not met expectations. From the target of 6 days, the realization was only 4.54 days. Another indicator that has not met expectations is the Net Death Rate (NDR) target of $\leq 32\%$ realization at 52.52. This is confirmed by the number of certified medical and non-media personnel. The number of certified medical and non-medical personnel is only 103 people from the 2020 target of 400 people. This indicates that the performance of employees at RSUD Dr. Zainoel Abidin needs serious attention.

One of the determinant variables of employee performance is High Work Performance (HWP). HWP or high-performance work practices provide a positive signal to employees that the organization pays attention to them to improve the quality and productivity of employees' work. This positive signal results in high employee output, and as a result organizational performance also increases (Silva & Chandrika, 2017).

Several other theories explain the influence of HWP and employee performance such as job characteristic models and equity theory. Equity theory explains that employees will be more motivated when they are treated fairly within the organization (Li et al., 2019). An almost similar thing is explained by the characteristic seat model which states that the strengthening of employee abilities is included in the equipment used to improve employee performance (Hackman & Oldham, 1976). Many studies have been conducted

recently that explains the theoretical Framework of hp's influence on employee performance in various countries and prove the influence of HWP on improving employee performance (Huang et al., 2017). In other strategic studies, researchers focus on the Manufacturing sector and ignore other sectors such as the service sector which is the fastest-growing sector of late. (Katou et al., 2014). Studies focused on the Manufacturing sector cannot be generalized to the service sector due to the fundamental characteristic differences between these two sectors such as production and consumption carried out simultaneously in the service sector but not in the production or manufacturing sectors and then there is high involvement from consumers at the stage of delivery of services produced by this sector (Liao et al., 2009).

The empirical gap shows that there is indeed an empirical phenomenon that occurs in RSUDZA, especially those related to employee performance. From the literature review, the author has been able to identify the causes of the phenomenon of low employee performance at RSUDZA, namely in the form of high-performance work practices, employee involvement, and employee extra roles.

1.2 Research Problem

The problem of this research is the relatively low performance of employees at Zainoel Abidin General Hospital, as evidenced by the fact that many general performance indicators are targeted but have not been achieved.

1.3 Research Objectives

To find out the determinant factors of employee performance at Zainoel Abidin General Hospital, and how they affect employee performance variables at this hospital. In addition, to find out whether there is a moderating role of employee extra role on the effect of high-performance work practices on employee performance.

2. THEORETICAL BACKGROUND AND HYPOTHESIS

2.1 High-Performance Work Practice (HWP)

Some studies related to hwp have provided many additional references to the study of literature related to this variable. Likewise, determinant factors are identified as the cause of the rise or fall of hwp such as empowerment, reward, and training. Others also indicated a close relationship between human rights and employee engagement. Karatepe (2013) in his research has also empirically tested the influence of these two variables. He managed to prove that empowerment reward and training are the main determinant variables in HWP. Almost the same thing is done by Zaman et al., (2020). He suggested that empowerment and training programs could significantly and positively reduce employee engagement. When employees at Empower use improper training programs, the results are not as expected. In another part of his research, he said that if given adequate compensation it will directly increase employee motivation in work and also increase the OCB. When employees

“The Impact of High Work Performance Practices on Hospital Employee Performance: The Mediation Moderation of Employee Engagement and Employee Extra Role”

are properly compensated, it can contribute to the growth and survival of the organization (Huang et al., 2017).

H1: There is an effect of high-performance work practices on employee engagement

H2: There is an effect of high-performance work practices on employee performance

2.2 Employee Engagement

Some literature has provided the fact that there is a close influence between employee engagement and employee performance. Karatepe (2013) said that employee engagement can improve the employee's performance. Engaged employees will be motivated to provide more services compared to what was done before or compared to what should be done related to service to customers.

Even frontline employees, if they feel engaged with the company then they will be more focused and pay above-average attention related to their duties in serving customers. including How Handling complaints are filed by customers so that their work provides quality output.

An engaged employee will show positive behavior in the workplace and will give dedication to the time he has, to complete the work charged to him in quality (Li et al., 2009)

According to Park et al., (2000) engagement is not actual behavior. But it reflects the level at which an employee is absorbed and pays tremendous attention so that it will have an impact on improving his or her performance. Park et al., (2000) continued from some existing literature he found that employee engagement will create positive in-role behavior and also the behavior of the employee as a whole. (Van De Voorde & Beijer, 2014)

H3: There is an effect of employee involvement on employee performance

H4: There is an effect of employee involvement mediating the relationship between high-performance work practices and employee performance

2.3 Employee Extra Role

Podsakoff et al., (2006) define extra-role behavior, or OCB as flexible behavior, and is usually not directly related to the rewards given by the company formally. However, the role of OCB is crucial because it can make a positive contribution to the formation of a good work culture within the company for example by assisting coworkers who have difficulty in carrying out their work. Performance in roles refers to the behavior of individuals performing the tasks required by the job (Albrecht, 2012) while the extra-role performance (employee extra-role) shows behavior outside the existing role (Zhang et al., 2013). Due to the increasingly fierce level of competition, hospitals require employees to carry out extra roles, one of which is to reduce costs, as an effort to increase the competitiveness of the hospital (Zhu, 2013).

Based on this statement, the writer includes the Extra Role variable as a moderator on the effect of high-performance work practice on employee performance. Performance in roles refers to the behavior of individuals performing the tasks required by the job (Reychav & Sharkie, 2010) while the extra-role performance (employee extra-role) shows behavior outside the existing role (Zhu, 2013). Due to the increasingly fierce level of competition, hospitals require employees to carry out extra roles, one of which is to reduce costs, as an effort to increase the competitiveness of the hospital (Zhu, 2013). Based on this statement, the author includes the Extra Role variable as a moderator on the effect of employee engagement on employee performance.

H5: There is a moderating role of employee extra role on the effect of high-performance work practices on employee performance

H6: There is a moderating role of employee extra role on the effect of employee involvement on employee performance

2.4 Employee Performance

Performance is a function of the motivation and ability of the employee in completing the work assigned to him. In a company, Every employee must have a certain level of ability and a certain desire to come together to make the best contribution to the survival of the company.

The level of ability and desire that the company expects will not be able to be given by employees if employees are not given adequate direction on how to behave in carrying out their work. Performance is a real behavior that can be seen from what is done by everyday employees in an organization. while the performance of the employee is related to the duties or mandates assigned to him to be completed as part of his contribution to the progress of the company. In other words, employee performance is the result of his work in quality and quantity achieved through the completion of the workload given to him which is his responsibility to be completed (Djatola, 2019).

2.5 Research Model

The model in this study is as figure 1 below.

Figure 1 Research Framework

3. RESEARCH METHOD

The population in this study were all civil servants at the Regional General Hospital dr. Zainoel Abidin, totaling 989 people. The sampling technique used in this study uses stratified

“The Impact of High Work Performance Practices on Hospital Employee Performance: The Mediation Moderation of Employee Engagement and Employee Extra Role”

probability sampling. The number of samples is 217 which is calculated using the slovin formula with an error rate of 5%. Primary data collection was conducted using a 5-point questionnaire on the Likert scale. In addition, it is also conducted in-depth interviews with several key informants, to confirm some issues that are considered importantly related to the theme of the matter being researched. Information from this in-depth interview can also be used to support the finding of quantitative analysis. The measurement of the High-Performance Work Practice variable uses 5 indicators from Karatepe (2013). Employee Engagement uses 4 indicators (Trevor et al., 2012). Then Employee Performance uses 5 indicators adopted from (Kahindi, 2021). Meanwhile, Employee Extra Role Behavior is measured using a measurement scale (Cropanzano et al., 2007).

Descriptive hypothesis testing was carried out using the average value of the respondents' perceptions of each variable. While testing the causalities hypothesis was carried out using a structural equation model with criteria $CR > 1.960$ and $P < 0.05$

4. RESEARCH RESULTS

4.1 Characteristics of Respondents

Characteristics of respondents based on gender are 87 male respondents or 40% and for female respondents 130 people or 60%. Characteristics of respondents based on age, namely for the age range <25 years there are 36 people or 20%, for the age range 21-25 years there are 56 people or 31%, for the age range 26-30 years there are 1 person or 0.5%, the age range is 26 – 30 years there were 21 people or 9.7%, and for the age range >40 years there were 83 people or 38.2%.

Characteristics of respondents based on marital status can be explained that as many as 17 respondents are unmarried, and 191 respondents are married. Thus, it can be explained that married respondents are more dominant than respondents who are not married. Regarding the working period of medical personnel at RSUD dr. Zainoel Abidin Banda Aceh, it can be explained that 14 respondents have a working period of fewer than 5 years, then as many as 31 respondents have a working period of 6-10 years, there are as many as 57 respondents have a working period of 11-15 years, respondents who have a working period of 16-20 years are as many as 70 people and respondents who have a working period of more than 20 years are 45 of the total respondents.

4.2 Research Instrument Tests

a. Validity test

The validity test aims to measure how effective an item is used as an indicator in measuring its variables. A variable measurement item is said to be valid if it can measure a variable with an adequate loading factor rate. Measurement of validity in this study using the construct validity test approach.

Table 1. Construct Validity Results using Unstandardized Regression Weight

	Est.	SE	CR	P
a20 <--- HWP	1,000			
a21 <--- HWP	1.106	,089	12,430	***
a22 <--- HWP	1.475	,092	15,957	***
a23 <--- HWP	1,458	,092	15.878	***
a24 <--- HWP	1,189	,087	13.638	***
a19 <--- EP	1,000			
a18 <--- EP	,996	,037	26,897	***
a17 <--- EP	1.002	0.035	28,331	***
a16 <--- EP	,939	,043	21,931	***
a15 <--- EP	,998	,039	25.561	***
a6 <--- EE	1,000			
a7 <--- EE	1.050	,082	12,830	***
a8 <--- EE	1.139	,078	14.516	***
a9 <--- EE	1.084	0.070	15,457	***
a14 <--- EmplXtra	1,000			
a13 <--- EmplXtra	,981	0.057	17,288	***
a12 <--- EmplXtra	,875	0.057	15,260	***
a11 <--- EmplXtra	1.022	0.059	17,414	***
a10 <--- EmplXtra	1.059	0.054	19,774	***

Based on Table 4.2, it can be explained that all the variables used in this study were declared valid, because they had a significance value of P-value (2-tailed 5%) < 0.05 so all indicators in the research variables were High Work Performance Practices, Employee Engagement, Employee This Performance and Employee Extra Role is declared valid to be continued at the next research stage.

4.3 Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA)

CFA is part of SEM analysis. SEM itself is a multivariate analysis tool that is said to have the ability to shake data that is fairly complex. This approach is also used to test the hypotheses built into this study. Hypothesis testing can only be done after the CFA is done first. The results of the CFA test turned out to be one indicator that was invalid because it had a loading factor value smaller than 0.5. The indicator is from the competency job variable, so it must be removed from the model.

Table 2. Confirmatory Factor Analysis

	Estimate
a20 <--- HWP	,747
a21 <--- HWP	,779
a22 <--- HWP	,964
a23 <--- HWP	,960
a24 <--- HWP	,845
a19 <--- EP	,921
a18 <--- EP	,943
a17 <--- EP	,956

“The Impact of High Work Performance Practices on Hospital Employee Performance: The Mediation Moderation of Employee Engagement and Employee Extra Role”

		Estimate
a16 <---	EP	,883
a15 <---	EP	,929
a6 <---	EE	,776
a7 <---	EE	,775
a8 <---	EE	,853
a9 <---	EE	,895
a14 <---	extra	,864
a13 <---	extra	,851
a12 <---	extra	,794
a11 <---	extra	,855
a10 <---	extra	,911

From the table above, it can be seen that none of them has a coefficient value below 0.5 or rounding up to 0.5. So, by factor loading, all existing indicators are said to have had a loading factor that is more than the required requirements, so it is said to be valid to be included in structural testing.

4.4 Goodness of Fit

In SEM analysis, model feasibility testing is a must. A model is said to be Fit if it can meet several required criteria, including CMIN / DF, RMSEA, TLI, IFI, and GFI. The results of the model feasibility test can be seen in the table below. The results of hypothesis testing using structural equation modeling can also be seen in the following table.

Table 3. Evaluation of Criteria for Goodness of Fit Indices

<i>The goodness of Fit Indices</i>	<i>Cut of value</i>	<i>Model Results</i>	<i>Information</i>
RMSEA	<0.08	0.067	<i>Good Fit</i>
CMIN/DF	<2.00	1,671	<i>Good Fit</i>
GFI	>0.90	0.914	<i>Fit</i>
AGFI	>0.90	0.883	<i>Marginal Fit</i>
TLI	>0.90	0.960	<i>Good Fit</i>
CFI	>0.90	0.960	<i>Good Fit</i>

Based on the table, it can be seen that the model is feasible to use because all goodness of fit values has a marginal fit condition and the rest are all fit. In an empirical study, a researcher is not required to fulfill all the goodness of fit criteria but depends on the judgment of each researcher. Marginal value is the condition of the suitability of the measurement model under the criteria of absolute fit and incremental fit. However, it can still be continued in further analysis because it is close to the goodness of fit criteria. Therefore, the model in this study as a whole can be said to be under the data and can be analyzed further.

4.5 Hypotheses Testing with Structural Model

Table 4. Results of Structural Equation Modeling Analysis

			Est.	SE	CR	P	Beta
EE <---	HWP		1.16	,10	11,5	***	,91
EP <---	EE		,43	,14	3,16	,002	,37
EP <---	HWP		,80	,18	4,52	***	,53

4.6 Direct Hypothesis Testing

Figure 2. Structural Model

H1. Influence of high-performance work practices on employee engagement

The results of testing the effect of high-performance work practices on employee engagement show a CR value of 11,467 and a probability of ***. The two values obtained have met the requirements for H1 acceptance, namely the CR value greater than 1.96 and the probability less than 0.05. Thus, it can be stated that the effect of high-performance work practices on employee engagement is significant.

The magnitude of the coefficient of the influence of high-performance work practices on employee engagement is 0.911 so the impact of high-performance work practices on employee engagement is significant at 91.1%.

H2. The effect of high-performance work practices on employee performance

The results of testing the effect of high-performance work practices on employee performance show a CR value of 4,527 and with a probability of ***. Both values obtained have met the requirements for H2 acceptance, namely the CR value greater than 1.96 and the probability less than 0.05. Thus, it can be stated that the effect of high-performance work practices on employee performance is significant. The magnitude of the influence of high-performing work practices on employee performance is 0.529 or 52.9%. So that the influence of high-performance work practices that are getting better will have an impact on employee performance

H3. Influence of employee engagement on employee performance

Testing There is an effect of employee involvement on employee performance showing the CR value of 3.166 and with

“The Impact of High Work Performance Practices on Hospital Employee Performance: The Mediation Moderation of Employee Engagement and Employee Extra Role”

a probability of 0.002. The two values obtained do not meet the requirements for H1 acceptance, namely the CR value greater than 1.96 and the probability less than 0.05. Thus, it can be stated that the effect of employee involvement on employee performance is significant. The magnitude of the coefficient of the influence of employee involvement on employee performance is 0.366 or 36.6%

4.7 Indirect Hypothesis Testing

H4. employee engagement mediates the relationship between high-performance work practices and employee performance

The results of testing the indirect effect of employee involvement mediating the relationship between high-performance work practices and employee performance have a Bootstrapping p-value score of 0.044. The value obtained has met the requirements for the acceptance of H_a , which is a probability less than 0.05. Thus, it can be stated that the effect of employee involvement mediating the relationship between high-performance work practices and employee performance is significant. The magnitude of the coefficient of the influence of employee involvement mediating the relationship between high-performance work practices and employee performance is 0.344 or 34.4%.

Figure 3. Indirect Effect

4.8 Moderation Hypotheses Testing

H5 There is a moderating role of employee extra role on the effect of high-performance work practices on employee performance

Figure 4. Moderation Effect

The results of testing the employee extra-role moderation hypothesis on the effect of high-performance work practices on employee performance show a significant number of effects indicated by the t-statistic value of

interaction moderation of 7324 and p-value of ***. The statistical t value and p-value exceed the required value so that the moderating role of the employee's extra role on the effect of high-performance work practices on employee performance is significant. In other words, the employee's extra role can be used as a catalyst in strengthening the influence of high-performance work practices on employee performance at the Dr. Zainoel Abidin Hospital Banda Aceh institution. The magnitude of the moderating effect of this interaction is 0.642 or 64.2%.

H.6 There is a moderating role of employee extra role on the effect of employee involvement on employee performance

The results of testing the employee extra-role moderation hypothesis on employee involvement in employee performance show an influence of 3,419 and a p-value of ***. The statistical t value and p-value exceed the required value so that the moderating role of the employee's extra role on the effect of employee involvement on employee performance is significant. In other words, the employee's extra-role can be used as a catalyst in strengthening the influence of employee involvement on employee performance at this Zainoel Abidin Hospital institution. The magnitude of the moderating effect of this interaction is 0.539 or 53.9%. This means that every time there is an increase in the perception of one positive unit of the extra role carried out by the employee, it will have an impact on increasing the effect of employee involvement on employee performance by 53.9% of the increase in the extra role.

4.9 Discussion

After going through a series of tests, all the direct hypotheses tested showed a significant effect. Of the three hypotheses tested, namely the effect of high-performance work practices on employee engagement, the effect of high-performance work practices on employee performance, and the effect of employee engagement on employee performance, all of them turned out to have a significant effect. When compared between these two determinant variables and their effect on employee performance, the independent variable high-performance practice (HWP) has a larger magnitude so that the impact it has on improving employee performance will be greater than employee involvement.

On the indirect effect, there is only one hypothesis that is tested, namely the influence of employee involvement mediating the relationship between high-performance work practices and employee performance. The results also show a significant effect. The role of employee engagement here is partial mediation because the direct influence of the two variables also shows significant results. This means that employee engagement besides being able to directly help improve the performance of employees at this RSUZA, indirectly also acts as a mediator on the influence of high-performing work practices on employee performance.

The last is testing the moderating role of the employee extra role in moderating the influence of the independent and dependent variable on employee performance, namely the

“The Impact of High Work Performance Practices on Hospital Employee Performance: The Mediation Moderation of Employee Engagement and Employee Extra Role”

moderating role of the employee extra role on the effect of high-performance work practices on employee performance and the moderating role of the employee extra role on the effect of employee involvement on employee performance. The results of testing these two moderating hypotheses also show significant results. In other words, the employee's extra role can increase the magnitude of the influence of high-performance work practices on employee performance and employee involvement in employee performance.

5. CONCLUSION

The variable that has the greatest impact on improving employee performance is high work performance practice with a coefficient of 0.529. While the employee engagement variable is only 0.366. This means that the increase in employee performance will be more effective if it is carried out through high work performance practices. The role of employee engagement will be better if it is positioned as a mediating variable. Tests on employee extra-role variables that moderate high work performance practice and employee engagement on employee performance also show significant results.

6. LIMITATION

Future research can develop a wider sample of hospital customers that is not only limited scope in one city but several cities within the Aceh province so that the findings will be more comprehensive.

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“The Impact of High Work Performance Practices on Hospital Employee Performance: The Mediation Moderation of Employee Engagement and Employee Extra Role”

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